

Table 1. Reaction to whitebacked planthopper of F₁ and F₂ populations from crosses of rice cultivars with TN1. University of Cantho, Vietnam, 1993.

Cross	F ₁ reaction	F ₂ seedlings				χ ²			P		
		Total (no.)	Resistant (no.)	Susceptible (no.)	(%)	3:1	15:1	13:3	3:1	15:1	13:3
TN1/IR2035-117-3	R	1379	1292	87	6	256.94	0.008	140.11	<0.01	90-95	<0.01
TN1/BR46	R	1471	1196	275	18	31.19	388.81	0.003	<0.01	<0.01	90-95
TN1/Xoai Cat	R	1468	1193	275	18	30.75	390.40	0.0003	<0.01	<0.01	95-99
TN1/Base	R	1221	912	309	25	0.06	756.79	34.46	80-90	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/Keo Cha A	R	1220	910	310	25	0.11	764.35	35.52	80-69	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/Rong Lem	R	1351	1005	346	25	0.27	864.26	41.74	60-70	<0.01	<0.01
TN1/La	R	1227	915	312	23	0.12	770.18	35.92	70-75	<0.01	<0.01

Table 2. Reaction to whitebacked planthopper of F₃ lines from crosses of rice cultivars with TN1. University of Cantho, Vietnam, 1993.

Cross	F ₃ lines (no.)				χ ²		P	
	Total	Resistant	Segregating	Susceptible	1:2:1	7:8:1	1:2:1	7:8:1
TN1/IR2035-117-3	335	147	167	21	94.79	0.003	<0.01	>99
TN1/BR46	334	150	162	22	98.41	0.31	<0.01	80-90
TN1/Xoai Cat	328	147	159	22	95.58	0.35	<0.01	80-90
TN1/Base	372	97	185	90	0.27	218.21	80-90	<0.01
TN1/Keo Cha A	374	95	181	98	0.43	267.22	75-85	<0.01
TN1/Rong Lem	363	90	177	96	0.42	266.83	75-85	<0.01
TN1/La	350	89	180	81	0.65	186.80	65-75	<0.01

populations from the crosses of TN1 with Base, Rong Lem, Keo Cha A, and La segregated in the ratio of 3 resistant to 1 susceptible, indicating that a single dominant gene confers resistance (Table 1).

In the cross TN1/IR2035-117-3, the F₂ populations segregated in the ratio of 15 resistant to 1 susceptible, indicating that two dominant genes governed resistance. The F₂ populations of the crosses of TN1/BR46 and TN1/Xoai Cat segregated in

the ratio of 13:3, suggesting that resistance in the two varieties was governed by one dominant and one recessive gene.

The results from the F₃ progenies confirmed the conclusion drawn from the F₂ data (Table 2). In all crosses, except TN1/Xoai Cat, TN1/BR46, and TN1/IR2035-117-3, the observed data agreed with the 1:2:1 resistant, segregating, susceptible ratio expected for monogenic control of resistance. The F₃ data from crosses of TN1/IR2035-117-3, TN1/BR46, and TN1/Xoai Cat agreed with the 7:8:1 ratio expected for digenic control of resistance. ■

Ratnagiri 3: a new gall midge-resistant, late-maturing variety from Maharashtra, India

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Gall midge incidence is a constraint that limits rice production in some areas. We undertook a program to develop high-yielding gall midge-resistant rice genotypes that mature late.

Cultivar Ratnagiri 3 was bred from the cross CR57-MR-1523/IR36/RTN 68. Maharashtra State released it for general cultivation in 1994. It is a semitall, long-duration variety (142 d) with long, bold grains.

In station trials from 1984 to 1986, Ratnagiri 3 outyielded the check variety in gall midge-endemic areas. In multi-location trials from 1987 to 1989, and

Table 1. Grain yield of Ratnagiri 3. Maharashtra, India. 1984-92.

Trial	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Ratnagiri 3 (RTN121)	Check ^a variety
Station trials, 1984-86 wet season	4.1	3.1
Multilocation trials, 1987-89 wet season (8 locations)	4.4	3.9
All India Coordinated Yield Trial	4.2	3.7
MRVT ^b 4 1988 wet season (12 locations)		
Field trial 1990-92 (34 locations)	4.4	3.5

^aVikram for station trials, Ratnagiri 68 for multilocation trials, Pankaj for MRVT 4, and Vidram for field trials. ^bMRVT = multiresistant variety trial.

Table 2. Ratnagiri 3 reactions to pests and diseases in multiresistant variety trial 4, 12 locations,^a 1988 wet season.

Variety	Reaction ^b						
	Disease				Insect pest		
	Blast	Bacterial leaf blight	Sheath blight	Brown spot	Gall midge 1	Gall midge 4	Stem borer
Ratnagiri 3	R	MR	MR	MR	R	R	MR
Pankaj	MR	S	MR	S	S	S	MR

^aLocations had high disease or insect pest pressure. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible.

field trials from 1990 to 1992, it outyielded the check variety (Table 1). In the All India Coordinated Yield Trials, it

ranked 7th out of 81 entries during 1988. Ratnagiri 3 has resistance to gall midge biotypes I and IV and blast disease and

moderate resistance to stem borer, bacterial leaf blight, sheath blight, and brown spot (Table 2). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Gan wan Xian 23 (Gan You Wan, SG89320): a new indica rice variety with high quality

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Gan wan Xian 23, released in May 1994 by the Jiangxi Provincial Seed Board, is a new semidwarf indica rice variety with high quality and other good traits. It was derived from the cross between IR841 and M79215, which is a strain from the cross Xi Dao 1/5450. The F_3 was irradiated with ^{60}Co γ -rays at the dose of 30 krad.

Gan wan Xian 23 is suitable for the later season in the double-cropped area of southern China and single-cropped area of central China. Because of its high quality, it won the gold medal prize at the First China Agriculture Exposition, sponsored by the Ministry of Agriculture in Oct 1992. In the double-cropped area, its average yield was 4.9-5.3 t/ha, which was 15% more than that of Shung Zhu Zheng, a check being used for the new high-quality evaluation in southern China. In the single-cropped area, the average yield of Gan wan Xian 23 was 5.3-6 t/ha.

The variety has strong stems, is 92-105 cm tall, and has a growth duration of 135-140 d. Gan wan Xian 23 has high yield potential under good irrigation and management conditions. It performed

Major quality traits of Gan wan Xian 23. Rice Research Institute of China, 1992.

Brown rice (%)	78-80.2
Milled rice recovery (%)	63-66.3
Head rice (%)	58-63
Kernel length (mm)	6.7
L:W ratio	3.3
Chalky kernel (%)	0
Area with chalkiness (%)	0
Amylose content (%)	15
Alkali spreading value	6.9
Gel consistency (mm)	90
Protein content of head rice (%)	7.0

well in regional trials, with yield reaching 6.3 t/ha in Hu Bei Province.

Gan wan Xian 23 has good resistance to blast disease. It has long, slender, translucent grains with intermediate amylose content, low gelatinization temperature, and soft gel consistency (see table). The cooked rice of Gan wan Xian 23 is soft and aromatic.

It has a 1,000 grain weight of 23-25.7 g, panicle length of 21.5-29.3 cm, and

88.7-116 field grains/panicle (82.5-91.8%). Gan wan Xian 23 is very popular among consumers in Hongkong. Its quality is at par with the high-quality Thai rices. Gan wan Xian 23 is being grown in Jiangxi, Hubei, Guangdong, Anhui, and Guanxi provinces, and is spreading quickly in other provinces of southern and central China. ■

Heibao, a high-yielding, good quality black indica rice for China

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Heibao is a newly released semidwarf indica variety with a black pericarp. It is derived from Dong-Lan-Mo-Mi/IR64 and has a 108-112 d duration. Heibao is highly cold tolerant at the seedling stage and is resistant to blast and bacterial blight. During the 1993 early season in Zhejiang, Jiangxi, Hubei, and Anhui, blast attacked many rice varieties but not Heibao. It has wide adaptability as an early rice in the double-cropped Yangtze River area.

Average yield at eight locations was 6.8 t/ha in 1993. The highest yield,

9.0 t/ha, was 25-40% more than the yields of the local black rice check varieties. Heibao has a 1,000-grain weight of 21.2 g, with 90% seed fertility.

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, cooking, and eating quality meet China's national index for high quality rice. Heibao's grain quality is superior to that of most black pericarp indica varieties in China. Grain length is 7.0 mm, with a 3.2 length-breadth ratio. Hulling recovery is 79%; milling recovery, 70.2%; and head rice recovery, 53%. Grain is semitranslucent with 19.3% amylose and 10.4% protein content. Four percent of the grain is chalky, with 0.2% area with chalkiness. It has intermediate gelatinization temperature and gel consistency (5.6 mm). Fe, P, Se, and other minerals are 3-5 times greater in Heibao than in ordinary rice. ■

Peiliangyou Teqing, a new high-yielding, two-line hybrid rice

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Peiliangyou Teqing (Pei'ai 64S/Teqing), developed by HHRRC, passed the examination of the Crop Variety Release Committee of Hunan Province in Jan 1994. It is the first two-line hybrid rice combination approved at the

provincial level for release to farmers in China.

Pei'ai 64S, the maternal parent, is a thermosensitive genic male sterile line bred from Nongken 58S/Pei'ai 64//Pei'ai 64. It shows pollen sterility of 99.98% and seed sterility of 100% based on a 50-panicle sample of 1,150 plants in 1990. It has a long sterile period: about 20 d at Shengyang, Beijing, and Guiyang; more than 50 d at Changsha; and nearly 80 d at Guangzhou—and even longer at Hainan.